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To cite this article: Ane Loroño Leturiondo *et al* 2026 *Environ. Res. Lett.* **21** 104032

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ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH
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Future health and economic impacts of extreme heat on older adults: a subnational analysis for Europe

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E-mail: ane.lorono@bc3research.org**Keywords:** climate health impacts, economic valuation, heat-related mortality, heat-related morbidity, projections, climatic and socio-economic scenarios, people over 65**Abstract**

This study quantifies the effects of rising temperatures due to climate change on the health of older adults and estimates the associated economic costs across 331 European regions. Using projections under climate and socio-economic pathways (SSP–RCP combinations), estimates are produced for 2030, 2050, and 2070. Mortality and morbidity figures do not differ greatly between scenarios in the short term, but they do in the long term. By 2070, mortality is estimated to range between 213 and 436 thousand cases in the low- and high-emission scenarios respectively, and morbidity is estimated to range between 127 and 261 thousand cases respectively in all of Europe. The short-term economic burden of morbidity is estimated at US\$312–332 million under low- and high-emission scenarios, increasing to US\$462–929 million by 2070. The willingness to pay to avoid morbidity events is valued at US\$189–204 billion in the short term and US\$283–581 billion by 2070. Mortality costs based on the value of a statistical life are projected to reach US\$774–825 billion (3.6%–4% of European GDP) in 2030 under SSP1–RCP2.6 and SSP5–RCP8.5, respectively, and up to US\$2.3 trillion (6.4% of GDP) by 2070 under high emissions, or half that amount under low emissions. When mortality is evaluated using the value of a life year, costs are lower yet remain substantial. These results highlight the urgent need for adaptation strategies and the strong economic benefits of emission mitigation, as well as the importance of localised responses to address regional vulnerabilities.

1. Introduction

Rising temperatures exacerbate pre-existing health conditions and contribute to the onset of new ones, especially cardiovascular, respiratory, renal and metabolic disorders, as well as mental-health disorders, infections and heat stress (Moghadamnia *et al* 2017, Schulte *et al* 2021). These impacts disproportionately affect vulnerable populations, including older adults, children, and people with chronic diseases or in situations of socioeconomic vulnerability. (Achebak *et al* 2024). The additional pressure on health systems is reflected in increased hospitalisations during episodes of extreme heat (Van Daalen *et al* 2022). The increasing frequency and intensity of these events therefore not only directly threaten human health but also amplify inequalities

and hamper the response capacity of health systems (An der Heiden *et al* 2020).

These effects are developing in a context of sustained warming: 2024 was the warmest year on record, 2025 ranked among the three warmest, and the last decade consistently appears as the warmest in the instrumental record ('Copernicus. Global Climate Highlights 2024' 2025). Climate projections point to even more worrying scenarios. Long-term projections suggest delays in emissions reductions lead to more severe, persistent heatwaves, with elevated heat exposure potentially continuing after net-zero targets are reached (Perkins-Kirkpatrick *et al* 2025).

Global attribution studies estimate that over one-third of warm-season heat-related deaths are attributable to anthropogenic climate change, with increased mortality reported across all continents

OPEN ACCESS

RECEIVED
14 February 2026REVISED
24 April 2026ACCEPTED FOR PUBLICATION
14 May 2026PUBLISHED
26 May 2026

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(Vicedo-Cabrera *et al* 2021). In summer 2022 alone, extreme heat caused over 61 000 deaths in Europe (Ballester *et al* 2023). Morbidity follows a similar pattern, with hospital admissions increasing as temperatures exceed critical thresholds (Adélaïde *et al* 2022, Achebak *et al* 2024). Although considerably less than mortality increases, demand for emergency services rises substantially (Paganini *et al* 2023). Economic costs are considerable; in France, between 2015 and 2019, direct heat-related medical costs were estimated at €10–280 million (Adélaïde *et al* 2022).

Unlike the vast evidence on mortality, research on morbidity is more limited (Achebak *et al* 2024), and studies that jointly analyse both impacts and their economic costs in Europe are scarce. This study addresses this gap by examining the effects of extreme heat on the European population aged 65 and over, integrating mortality and morbidity risks and their economic implications. To this end, CMIP6 climate models and socioeconomic projections under four SSP–RCP combinations (SSP1–RCP2.6, SSP2–RCP4.5, SSP3–RCP7.0 and SSP5–RCP8.5) are used. Costs are estimated using two approaches for mortality (VSL and VOLY) and two for morbidity (WTP and medical cost), with regional results at NUTS3 level for the 27 European Union countries. By combining these elements, the study aims to contribute to a more integrated assessment of the health and economic impacts of extreme heat in Europe.

2. Method

2.1. Mortality impact assessment

To estimate the effect of climate change on heat-related mortality, we employed an established model that links all-cause mortality to temperature projections under various climate scenarios (Honda *et al* 2014, World Health Organization, 2014). In the present study, the analysis focuses specifically on individuals aged 65 and older. The baseline period has been defined as 1995–2015.

Baseline and future projections of all-cause annual mortality data were obtained from Eurostat³ for the years 2030, 2050, and 2070 at the NUTS3 level for people over 65. The database comprised data for 1,216 regions across the European Union.

The relative risk of heat-related mortality under climate change was obtained from the World Bank Climate Change Knowledge Portal⁴ (WBCKKP) at the European subnational level using the latest CMIP6 climate data under four SSP–RCP scenarios (SSP1–RCP2.6, SSP2–RCP4.5, SSP3–RCP7.0, SSP5–RCP8.5), including relative risk estimates for the 10th,

50th (median), and 90th temperature percentiles, covering 366 regions at NUTS2 and NUTS3 levels across 27 countries. This data is available as supplementary material in the Zenodo repository (see data availability section).

Eurostat and WBCKKP regions were matched to produce a final dataset of 331 subnational units across 27 EU countries; analyses were performed at the NUTS3 level where possible, and NUTS2 where relative risk data were only available at that level, and were conducted at the country level for Latvia, Luxembourg, Cyprus, and Malta (see appendix A for details).

2.2. Morbidity impact assessment

The methodology follows Adélaïde *et al* (2022), who, using French data, estimated excess deaths during heatwaves and excess morbidity by healthcare cause (including faintness, hyponatremia, hyperthermia, heat stroke, isolated fever and dehydration), and classified the medical-care system into four subcategories: emergency visits to primary hospitals with and without subsequent hospitalisation, and outpatient visits to secondary and tertiary hospitals with and without hospital follow-up.

We applied the empirical relationship between heat-related mortality and morbidity from Adélaïde *et al* (2022) to estimate morbidity by extracting ratios between excess deaths and excess healthcare cases for each of the four care subcategories and applying them to heat-attributable mortality estimates across the 331 regions.

2.3. Estimating the economic costs of heat-related impacts on health

In the literature, estimates of premature mortality typically rely on two metrics: the value of a statistical life (VSL) and the value of a life year lost (VOLY). The former is derived from the willingness to pay (WTP) to mitigate mortality risk, while the latter represents the WTP to avert the loss of a year of life (Chiabai *et al* 2018, Adélaïde *et al* 2022). In this study, both measures are used.

The baseline VSL of US\$4.5 million per person (2017 prices) was taken from OECD (2012), while VOLY estimates of US\$99 769–239 825 (2017 prices) for the EU28 were taken from Holland (2024); both were adjusted using regional GDP per capita. Country baseline GDP obtained from Eurostat⁵ was projected using growth forecasts under each socio-economic scenario⁶. For VOLY-based cost estimates, since values are per year of life lost, life expectancy by 5 year age group (65–69 through 95+) was applied and multiplied by excess heat-related deaths to estimate years of life lost per region.

³ Eurostat: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/proj_19rdth3/default/table?lang=en&category=proj.proj_19r.

⁴ World Bank Climate Change Knowledge Portal: <https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/>.

⁵ Eurostat: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/nama_10r_2gdp_custom_9865023/default/table.

⁶ IIASA: <https://data.ece.iiasa.ac.at/ssp/#/workspaces>.

For morbidity, we analysed the costs based on the WTP for the avoidance of the healthcare case, as well as the medical costs of each type of healthcare. Estimates of WTP were taken from Ready *et al* (2004), based on a survey conducted in five European countries. As in Adélaïde *et al* (2022), we used the average of these country-specific estimates as a proxy for WTP in the European countries included in this analysis.

Concerning medical costs, given the variation between countries, we collected data on the financial implications of hospitalisation in European countries from the World Health Organization⁷. We assumed an average hospital stay of 6.7 d following Adélaïde *et al* (2022), while outpatient visits remain cost-neutral, assuming no stay at the hospital (appendix B).

An open-access database has been created containing all estimates made (health impact and costs) for each year (historical and projections), for each scenario (the four SSP–RCP combinations) and for each relative risk (p10, p90 and median temperature). Figure 1 provides a graphical explanation of the methodology and all the information available on the database as a result of this study.

3. Results

3.1. Future health impacts

Results project European heat-related deaths at 142 165–153 273 by 2030 under SSP1–RCP2.6 and SSP5–RCP8.5, respectively. Equal to 0.13% of the 65+ population and nearly double the 72 995 baseline deaths; by 2050, deaths rise to 208 037–281 511 (0.15%–0.21%), and by 2070 reach 436 533 ($\approx 0.32\%$) under SSP5–RCP8.5. Compared with baseline, deaths are 3.5 times higher in 2070 under SSP1–RCP2.6, 2.2 times higher in 2030 under SSP5–RCP8.5, and more than 7 times higher by 2070, with scenario differences widening over time.

Heat-related morbidity in Europe varies by care type (emergency vs outpatient) and by whether hospitalisation occurs; under the ‘middle-of-the-row’, SSP2–RCP4.5, scenario, emergency visits with hospitalisation total 83 057 cases in the short term and 154 340 in the long term, while emergency visits without hospitalisation are higher, at 167 572 and 311 388, respectively. Outpatient visits with hospitalisation are much lower (4371 short-term; 8123 long-term), whereas outpatient visits without hospitalisation reach 64 114–119 140 episodes; overall, most heat-related healthcare demand comes from

emergency care without hospitalisation, and all categories increase over time.

Scenario-specific estimates are reported in appendix C, while figure 2 presents country-level SSP2–RCP4.5 projections of mortality and morbidity for 2030 and 2070 across all EU-27 countries; scenario differences are modest in the short term but diverge markedly in long-term mortality and morbidity depending on the emissions and socioeconomic pathway.

The heat-related mortality and morbidity was estimated for each European region (331 regions overall). The results obtained for each region under each scenario are collected in the database accessible at the Zenodo repository. See ‘Data availability’ section.

3.2. Future heat-related mortality costs

Figure 3 illustrates the projected economic costs associated with heat-related mortality in Europe for the years 2030, 2050, and 2070 under four climate and socioeconomic scenarios (SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5, SSP3-7.0, and SSP5-8.5). Under the VSL framework, economic costs increased markedly over time, particularly under higher-emission scenarios. In 2030, the estimated financial burden ranges from US\$771 to US\$824 billion across scenarios, corresponding to approximately 3.6%–4.0% of projected European GDP. By 2050, costs are expected to rise substantially to between US\$1.5 trillion and US\$2.4 trillion, representing around 5%–7% of EU GDP. In the long term, projected costs could reach between US\$1.9 trillion and US\$5.5 trillion by 2070, equivalent to roughly 5%–10% of Europe’s future GDP.

Differences across climate scenarios are small in the near term but widen markedly over time: 2030 estimates are similar, whereas divergences grow by 2050 and are especially pronounced by 2070, with the grey shaded area (see figure 3) indicating a gap of about US\$3.6 trillion between high-emissions and strong-mitigation pathways, highlighting the economic benefits of mitigation.

When impacts are assessed using the VOLY approach, which accounts for remaining life expectancy at the time of death, estimated costs are considerably lower than those obtained using the VSL framework, reflecting differences in the underlying valuation of welfare losses. In 2030, VOLY-based costs range between US\$187 billion and US\$451 billion under SSP1-2.6, corresponding to approximately 0.85% of Europe’s GDP. Under the high-emissions SSP5-8.5 scenario, costs increase to between US\$200 and US\$481 billion, representing about 2.5% of GDP in the same year.

Although absolute values are lower under the VOLY metric, temporal trends and relative scenario differences closely match those under VSL, with costs rising steadily over time and scenario gaps widening

⁷ WHO-Choice database: [www.who.int/teams/health-systems-governance-and-financing/economic-analysis/costing-and-technical-efficiency/quantities-and-unit-prices-\(cost-inputs\)/econometric-estimation-of-who-choice-country-specific-costs-for-inpatient-and-outpatient-health-service-delivery](http://www.who.int/teams/health-systems-governance-and-financing/economic-analysis/costing-and-technical-efficiency/quantities-and-unit-prices-(cost-inputs)/econometric-estimation-of-who-choice-country-specific-costs-for-inpatient-and-outpatient-health-service-delivery).

toward the end of the century; by 2070, the difference between SSP5–8.5 and low-emission scenarios reaches about US\$250 billion at the lower bound and roughly US\$600 billion at the upper bound.

Figure 4 presents the distribution of heat-related mortality costs across European countries in the short and long term (2030 and 2050), expressed as a

percentage of national GDP. In the short term, differences across climate scenarios are relatively limited at the country level, with noticeable divergence emerging only under the high-emissions SSP5–8.5 scenario. Under the VSL framework, moderate heterogeneity across countries is already apparent in 2030, with costs ranging from below 1% of GDP in countries

such as Cyprus and Malta to values exceeding 4%–5% of GDP in Austria, Belgium, Finland, France, and Germany.

By 2070, substantial discrepancies emerge both across countries and across climate scenarios. In most

countries, the cost of heat-related mortality is approximately twice as high under SSP5-8.5 compared to SSP2-4.5, indicating a strong sensitivity of economic impacts to the chosen climate pathway. The highest relative costs are observed in Luxembourg, followed

by Austria and Italy, while Cyprus, Ireland, Bulgaria, and Malta consistently exhibit the lowest costs relative to GDP.

A detailed scenario comparison indicates that by 2070 the gap in mortality costs between low-

and high-emissions pathways exceeds 0.4 percentage points of GDP in Belgium, Finland, Latvia, Greece, Slovakia, Spain, Austria, and Ireland, but remains below 0.3 points in Romania, the Czech Republic, Estonia, Bulgaria, Italy, Lithuania, Poland,

Figure 5. Projected total morbidity costs in Europe for selected future years under four climate scenarios, estimated using medical costs and WTP approaches. The long-term difference between the SSP1–RCP2.6 and SSP5–RCP8.5 scenarios is also shown.

Table 1. Future morbidity costs in Europe under different climate scenarios, showing short- and long-term costs for each type of morbidity, and differentiating between hospitalisation and non-hospitalisation for both medical costs and WTP. Data are shown in million US\$.

	SSPI-2.6		SSP2-4.5		SSP3-7.0		SSP5-8.5	
	2030	2070	2030	2070	2030	2070	2030	2070
Medical costs								
Emergency visits	10	15	11	19	10	23	11	31
Outpatient visits	3	5	3	6	3	7	3	9
Hospitalisation	299	442	305	558	291	672	318	889
WTP								
Emergency visits	49	74	50	94	48	114	53	151
Hospitalisation	140	210	143	266	137	325	151	429

Luxembourg, and Cyprus, indicating lower pathway sensitivity there; Luxembourg nevertheless shows the highest heat-related mortality costs despite not having disproportionately higher mortality incidence.

3.3. The costs of future heat-related morbidity

Figure 5 shows the total economic costs of heat-related morbidity in Europe under four climate scenarios for 2030 and 2070, comparing direct medical costs and WTP estimates. Under both approaches, costs rise substantially over time and are higher under high-emissions scenarios. Medical cost estimates increase from about US\$312–332 million in 2030 to US\$462–929 million by 2070, while WTP estimates grow from roughly US\$185–204 million to US\$283–581 million. Scenario differences are modest in 2030 but become much more pronounced by 2070.

Table 1 details heat-related morbidity costs by type and valuation approach. In all scenarios, hospitalisations represent the largest share, far exceeding emergency and outpatient visits. Under the medical cost approach, hospitalisation costs rise from about

US\$299–318 million in 2030 to US\$442–889 million by 2070, peaking under SSP5-8.5. WTP estimates are consistently higher for each morbidity outcome, reflecting broader welfare valuation, though the relative shares across categories remain similar. Scenario differences are small in 2030 but widen markedly by 2070.

Figures 6 and 7 show the regional distribution of heat-related morbidity costs per 1000 inhabitants in Europe under the medical cost and WTP approaches for 2030, 2050, and 2070 under low- and high-emissions scenarios. Although absolute values differ, both methods display consistent spatial and temporal patterns. Under the low-emissions scenario (SSP1–RCP2.6), costs remain relatively low and stable, with moderate increases from 2030 to 2070. Under the high-emissions scenario (SSP5–RCP8.5), costs rise substantially across most regions from mid-century, with a clear expansion and intensification of high-cost areas by 2070, especially in Western, Central, and Southern Europe. As with mortality, Luxembourg shows the highest morbidity costs despite not necessarily having a disproportionately higher incidence.

Figure 6. Map of Europe (NUTS3 level) showing hospitalisation medical costs (US\$ per 1000 inhabitants) under different climate scenarios, for both short- and long-term horizons.

Figure 7. Map of Europe (NUTS3 level) showing hospitalisation WTP-based costs (US\$ per 1000 inhabitants) under different climate scenarios, for both short- and long-term horizons.

Overall, the regional analysis reveals strong spatial heterogeneity in heat-related morbidity costs across Europe and shows that both their magnitude and spatial extent are highly sensitive to the climate pathway. The close agreement between the medical cost and WTP results suggests that the regional patterns are robust to the valuation method used.

4. Discussion

4.1. Comparison with previous estimates

During the 1995–2015 baseline period, we estimate over 72 000 annual deaths attributable to heat across Europe. This figure exceeds recent mortality estimates for the summer of 2022 (Ballester *et al* 2023) but is comparable to those recorded during the extreme summer of 2003 (Robine *et al* 2008).

Table 2 shows country-level differences between our estimates and those of Ballester *et al* (2023). Our results are generally lower in Southern Europe and higher in Northern Europe, a pattern likely driven by differences in methodological thresholds. Heat-related mortality is typically estimated using either the minimum mortality temperature or the threshold above which mortality rises significantly. In this study, we assume, following Honda *et al* (2014), that mortality is minimal at the 84th temperature percentile and increases beyond it. Other studies, such as Linares-Gil *et al* (2024), determine this threshold empirically for each Spanish region, revealing substantial regional variability.

Our approach—applying a uniform 84th percentile temperature threshold across Europe—offers a distinct perspective. While our aggregated European estimate is higher than that of Ballester *et al* (2023), this difference does not imply systematic overestimation, as our results are lower in several Southern European countries and higher in Northern regions (table 2), reflecting methodological differences in threshold definition and exposure assessment. Although our continental estimates are generally higher than some previous studies, we do not overestimate mortality in all regions. In warmer areas, a fixed percentile may capture health impacts that begin earlier or persist longer than region-specific methods. This underscores the sensitivity of mortality outcomes to threshold selection and the importance of accounting for regional climatic variability.

For instance, while the Spanish Carlos III Health Institute (Linares-Gil *et al* 2024) uses region-specific percentiles between 77 and 98 to define statistically significant mortality increases, our fixed 84th percentile may yield higher estimates where the true threshold is higher and lower estimates where it is lower. Moreover, our analysis includes only individuals aged 65 and over, which may reduce regional-level estimates. Nevertheless, when aggregated nationally,

our results closely align with Linares-Gil *et al* (2024)'s overall estimates of heat-attributable mortality in Spain.

Under SSP1–RCP2.6 and SSP5–RCP8.5, our baseline mortality is projected to increase 5- to 13-fold, respectively. Similarly, Díaz *et al* (2019) estimate a 10-fold rise in mortality for 2051–2100 compared to 2000–2009, with annual deaths reaching 12 896 (95% CI: 9852–15976) by century's end. For 2050, we project 208 037–281 511 annual heat-related deaths in Europe. Masselot *et al* (2025) report 36 deaths per 100 000 inhabitants for that year—about 253 000 deaths based on a projected population of 703 million—within our estimated range. This convergence, despite differences in temperature thresholds and exposure assumptions, suggests a similar order of magnitude for future heat-related mortality across Europe.

By 2070, our estimates indicate that heat-induced deaths in the EU could reach 213 136 (142181–300615) under SSP1-2.6 and 436 533 (284927–685,108) under SSP5-8.5. Likewise, Masselot *et al* (2025) project around 390,000 excess annual deaths under SSP3-7.0. Which would be in line with our rates. Although our figures are slightly higher than those of Díaz *et al* (2019), both studies show that mortality growth is not linear, underscoring the complex relationship between climate change and heat-related health risks.

4.2. Population ageing effect

Changes in the demographic pyramid must also be considered when estimating heat-attributable mortality among those aged 65 and over. Eurostat population projections show a rising share of this age group until 2050, reaching 24% in 2030 and 29% in 2050, potentially contributing to higher overall mortality. However, after 2050, the proportion stabilises at around 30%, while heat-attributable mortality continues to increase. These changes have been taken into account in our projections.

4.3. Population migration

Our projections rely on Eurostat population estimates that do not account for potential future redistributions associated with climate-related migration. While climate factors are increasingly recognised as one driver of population mobility, the direction and magnitude of their effect on regional populations in Europe remain highly uncertain. The available evidence suggests that most climate-related migration is internal to national borders (Rigaud *et al* 2018) and that climate hazards rarely act as the sole trigger for mobility decisions (Ionesco *et al* 2016, Ghosh and Orchiston 2022). In regions where extreme heat becomes a significant push factor, our estimates could overstate future mortality burdens if populations partially relocate; conversely, concentration of vulnerable migrants in urban heat islands could lead

Table 2. Country-level comparison of our estimates of heat-attributable mortality with those reported by Ballester *et al* (2023), expressed as a percentage of total mortality in each country.

Country	Annual mortality for all causes			Excess deaths			
	Source: Eurostat 2022	Ballester <i>et al</i> 2023		This study estimates baseline period		This study estimates 2030 SSP1-2.6	
	No. Of deaths	No. Of deaths	% of total mortality	No. Of deaths	% of total mortality	No. Of deaths	% of total mortality
<i>Southern and Eastern Europe</i>							
Italy	715 077	18 010	2.5%	6689	0.9%	14 865	2%
Spain	461 954	11 324	2.4%	5110	1.1%	12 427	2.6%
Greece	139 921	3092	2.2%	1073	0.8%	2843	2%
Portugal	124 311	2212	1.7%	1381	1.1%	1471	1.2%
Malta	4230	76	1.7%	11	0.2%	52	1.2%
Cyprus	7295	101	1.3%	24	0.3%	70	0.9%
Bulgaria	118 814	1277	1%	1368	1.1%	2671	2.2%
Croatia	56 979	731	1.2%	800	1.4%	1652	2.8%
Romania	272 953	2455	0.8%	3387	1.2%	6591	2.4%
<i>Centre and North Europe</i>							
Slovenia	22 492	154	0.6%	283	1.2%	716	3.1%
Hungary	136 823	513	0.3%	2134	1.5%	4085	2.9%
Austria	93 332	419	0.4%	1407	1.5%	3003	3.2%
France	675 271	4807	0.7%	9753	1.4%	20 131	2.9%
Germany	1066 341	8173	0.7%	20 179	1.8%	35 299	3.3%
Belgium	116 424	434	0.3%	2172	1.8%	3629	3.1%
Poland	448 448	763	0.1%	6249	1.3%	12 452	2.7%
Denmark	59 435	252	0.4%	673	1.1%	1262	2.1%
Lithuania	42 884	381	0.8%	679	1.5%	1024	2.3%
Ireland	35 000	26	0.7%	513	1.4%	491	1.4%
Estonia	17 315	167	0.9%	232	1.3%	418	2.4%
Finland	63 219	225	0.3%	1186	1.8%	2135	3.3%
Europe	5158 349	61 672	1.11%	72 995	1.14%	142 165	2.75%

to underestimation in destination areas. Integrating population redistribution dynamics into heat-health impact models represents an important avenue for future research.

4.4. Heat adaptation: methodological considerations and sensitivity analysis

A key factor in projecting future heat-related mortality and morbidity is the extent to which populations adapt to rising temperatures over time. Our main analysis addresses this issue by applying a constant percentile threshold (the 84th percentile of the local temperature distribution) to define heat exposure across all future scenarios. As this threshold is defined in relative rather than absolute terms, it shifts upwards in line with projected temperature increases, implicitly reflecting a process of population acclimatisation. Within this framework, the frequency of days exceeding the threshold remains stable over time despite warming, meaning that the projected burden reflects increases in the intensity of heat exposure rather than increases in its frequency. This approach corresponds to what the literature defines as a scenario of complete adaptation to heat. Specifically,

Martinez *et al* (2018) and Diaz *et al* (2019) explicitly distinguish between a no-adaptation scenario—in which the absolute threshold temperature remains fixed over time—and a full adaptation scenario—in which the percentile of the temperature series corresponding to the threshold is assumed to remain constant. Our main analysis follows the latter. This is in contrast to studies such as Guo *et al* (2018), which assume a constant absolute threshold and therefore implicitly represent an upper bound of impact under a no-adaptation assumption. Further methodological support is provided by Gosling *et al* (2017), who conducted the first systematic comparison of six adaptation modelling methods across 14 European cities and characterised the fixed-percentile approach as equivalent to complete acclimatisation; they also demonstrate that adaptation modelling uncertainty is, in most cities, a larger source of variability in projected impacts than either climate model or emissions scenario uncertainty—underscoring the importance of making adaptation assumptions explicit.

We acknowledge, however, that complete acclimatisation represents an optimistic assumption, and that real-world adaptation encompasses broader societal processes that may not be fully captured by a

shifting temperature threshold alone. These include public health interventions such as heat-health warning systems, improvements in housing conditions and access to cooling, behavioural changes, and broader socioeconomic development. It is also worth noting that, while the fixed-percentile method captures full physiological acclimatisation, Gosling *et al* (2017) caution that this approach does not entirely eliminate the additional mortality burden from climate change, as it does not fully account for changes in the shape of the future temperature distribution. Our estimates should therefore be interpreted with this caveat in mind.

To explore the potential influence of broader adaptation processes on our estimates, we conducted a sensitivity analysis at the aggregated European level. Following the empirical adaptation rates reported by Gallo *et al* (2024)—who estimated that heat-related mortality in Europe in 2023 would have been approximately 80% higher in the absence of societal adaptation measures observed between 2000 and 2019—we applied this figure as an upper-bound scenario representing the maximum plausible additional adaptation effect beyond physiological acclimatisation. Results are presented in table 3 for each projection horizon (2030, 2050, 2070) and SSP–RCP scenario. With such a level of adaptation, excess deaths decline considerably. Given the substantial uncertainty surrounding future adaptation trajectories, however, this scenario should be interpreted as a sensitivity check rather than a central projection.

4.5. Low values of morbidity estimates compared to mortality

Although morbidity rates are much lower than mortality rates, with rising temperatures, the literature shows a relationship between temperature and hospital admissions, highlighting the negative impact of heat waves on emergency medical care (Li *et al* 2015).

For all ages and causes, each degree above the 36.5 °C threshold in Madrid is associated with a 21.5% increase in mortality, whereas hospital admissions rose by no more than 5% (Linares and Díaz 2008). Similar patterns appear elsewhere: during the 2003 London heatwave, mortality among those over 75 increased by 59%, while admissions rose by 16% (Johnson *et al* 2005). Arbuthnott and Hajat (2017) likewise compile historical UK data on temperature-related mortality and morbidity.

4.6. Estimating heat-related morbidity

A key contribution of this study is the estimation of heat-related morbidity at the subnational level across Europe, alongside associated economic costs—an area where empirical evidence remains scarce. While the mortality impacts of heat have been widely studied, morbidity has received comparatively less attention, particularly in spatially explicit and forward-looking analyses. In this context,

our approach is intended to provide an order-of-magnitude assessment that complements mortality estimates and enables a more comprehensive evaluation of the overall health burden of heat.

The estimation of morbidity is based on a mortality-to-morbidity ratio derived from French data (Adélaïde *et al* 2022). This choice is driven by data limitations: harmonised, subnational time series of heat-related hospitalisations are not currently available across Europe, and most existing studies report either mortality or morbidity, but not both within a consistent analytical framework.

To assess the robustness of this approach, we conducted a targeted literature review to identify alternative sources reporting both mortality and morbidity outcomes. Evidence from Québec (Boudreault *et al* 2024) provides a useful point of comparison, as it distinguishes between hospitalisations and emergency department visits. While hospitalisation-to-mortality ratios reported in that study are broadly consistent with our estimates, substantially higher ratios are observed when emergency visits are included, highlighting the sensitivity of results to the definition of health outcomes and healthcare system characteristics.

In this context, we adopt the France-based ratio as a pragmatic and contextually relevant approximation for Europe. Compared to alternative estimates, it provides an initial representation of morbidity impacts, grounded in a European healthcare and demographic setting.

Rather than aiming to provide precise morbidity estimates, this approach captures the broader magnitude of heat-related health impacts and allows the integration of morbidity into the overall burden assessment. This is particularly important for economic analyses, where excluding morbidity would lead to a substantial underestimation of total costs, especially those with fiscal ramifications. By incorporating morbidity within a consistent modelling framework, our study contributes to bridging the gap between epidemiological evidence and integrated impact assessment, while also highlighting the need for more comprehensive and harmonised data across regions.

4.7. Uncertainties and limitations

Although Eurostat population projections were used, variations such as ageing were not considered; incorporating this factor could improve the analysis. Environmental factors like humidity and air pollution were also excluded, despite their potential influence (López-Bueno *et al* 2025, Ruiz-Paez *et al* 2025). Both health impact estimates and economic valuations involve uncertainty (Adélaïde *et al* 2022). In addition, it is important to recognise that large-scale climate models, including CMIP6 projections, do not explicitly account for urban heat island effects, local microclimatic variability, or indoor heat exposure,

Table 3. Sensitivity analysis for heat adaptation: projected heat-related mortality in Europe under main estimates and under a full adaptation scenario (80% reduction following Gallo *et al* 2024), by projection year and SSP–RCP scenario.

	Heat-related mortality cases in Europe							
	This study's main estimates				Full adaptation scenario (–80% reduction) based on Gallo <i>et al</i> 2024			
	SSP1-2.6	SSP2-4.5	SSP3-7.0	SSP5-8.5	SSP1-2.6	SSP2-4.5	SSP3-7.0	SSP5-8.5
2030	141 211	144 724	138 189	152 236	28 242	28 945	27 638	30 447
2050	206 792	219 402	225 019	279 769	41 358	43 880	45 004	55 954
2070	211 673	268 957	328 419	433 648	42 335	53 791	65 684	86 730

all of which can significantly influence actual heat exposure and associated health risks. As a result, our estimates may not fully capture these locally relevant factors, and should be interpreted with this limitation in mind.

Economic values also reflect uncertainty due to variation in individuals' WTP (Adélaïde *et al* 2022). Country-specific values were derived using a range of estimates, but hospitalisation costs vary by age, length of stay, and season, so more detailed data would reduce uncertainty in future assessments.

Adaptation is not explicitly modelled other than by using a relative threshold. Evidence shows some adjustment through acclimatisation, behavioural change, and improved policies and health systems, reflected in higher minimum mortality temperatures and declining heat risks (Díaz *et al* 2019, Navas-Martín *et al* 2023). Its pace, distribution, and limits, however, remain uncertain (Navas-Martín *et al* 2022a, 2022b).

Despite these limitations, we argue that the methodology provides robust regional and overall European estimates and is globally applicable, combining World Bank relative risks with CMIP6 climate data to project economic impacts for 2030, 2050, and 2070 under different SSP–RCP scenarios.

5. Conclusions

This study shows that heat-related health impacts already impose substantial near-term economic costs that escalate sharply over time. Under a mid-range scenario (SSP2–RCP4.5), mortality costs exceed US\$700 billion by 2030, while heat-related hospitalisation costs reach around US\$300 million. Under a high-emissions pathway (SSP5–RCP8.5) by 2070 both mortality and morbidity costs are projected to nearly triple, highlighting the significant health and economic co-benefits of effective mitigation and adaptation.

Across all scenarios and valuation approaches, mortality represents the dominant share of total costs. Using the VSL, annual mortality costs increase from US\$1.9 trillion under SSP1-2.6 to US\$5.5 trillion under SSP5-8.5 by 2070, implying mitigation benefits of about US\$3.6 trillion annually. VOLY-based estimates are lower but follow the same pattern, rising

from US\$0.6 trillion to US\$1.0 trillion, corresponding to benefits of roughly US\$0.4 trillion.

Although much smaller than mortality costs, morbidity is economically and fiscally significant as it reflects increased needs of health care systems. It also grows non-linearly. By 2070, WTP-based estimates increase from US\$283 million under low emissions to US\$581 million under high emissions, while direct medical costs rise from US\$462 million to US\$929 million, yielding mitigation benefits of nearly US\$300 million and over US\$400 million, respectively. Relative to baseline conditions, morbidity costs roughly double by 2030, triple under low-emissions pathways, and increase up to sevenfold under high-emissions scenarios by the end of the century, reflecting compounding effects of rising heat exposure, population ageing, and healthcare demand.

The spatial analysis shows that the economic impacts of heat-related mortality and morbidity are unevenly distributed across Europe and become increasingly differentiated over time under different climate scenarios. Economic hotspots do not necessarily coincide with the highest epidemiological burden, but reflect a combination of health impacts and local economic structures, including healthcare prices and income levels. This highlights the need to interpret spatial cost patterns alongside physical health indicators when comparing regions and countries.

Luxembourg illustrates this pattern: it consistently records the highest heat-related costs without a disproportionately higher incidence. Per capita costs are strongly shaped by country-specific healthcare prices, closely linked to income levels and wage structures. In high-income countries such as Luxembourg, higher unit costs for hospitalisation, outpatient care, and medication generate elevated per capita costs even with comparable health outcomes.

Overall, the results show that climate change is not a distant or abstract threat but a tangible and growing economic burden for European societies. Future health-related costs—affecting public budgets and population welfare—depend critically on the ambition and effectiveness of mitigation policies implemented today. Across all impact categories and valuation methods, delayed or weak mitigation results in substantially higher losses, whereas strong mitigation delivers major health co-benefits, with avoided costs reaching several trillion US dollars

annually by 2070. These findings underscore the central role of climate mitigation in limiting future heat-related health impacts and their economic consequences, particularly for Europe's older population.

Acknowledgments

This research is supported by the European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101081358 for the project ACCREU (Assessing Climate Change Risk in Europe). It has also received funding from the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO) through BC3 María de Maeztu excellence accreditation MDM-2017-0714, from the Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities (MCIU) under Grant No. PID2024-160087NB-I00 and from the Basque Government through the BERC 2018-2021 programme and Grant No. IT7777-22.

Data availability

All the results obtained in this study have been compiled in an open-access database. These estimates can be found for 331 regions in 27 European countries. For the reference period and for projections for the years 2030, 2050 and 2070 in four different climate and socio-economic scenarios (SSP1-RCP2.6, SSP2-RCP4.5, SSP3-RCP7.0 and SSP5-RCP8.5).

The databases can be found in the Zenodo repository. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ae6dd6>.

Ethical statement

No ethical approval was required for this research.

Appendix A. Regions included in the study

Table A1. Summary of NUTS regions included in the analysis.

Country	NUTS level	Eurostat code(s)	Region name(s)	World bank climate portal region
Belgium (BE)	NUTS 1	BE1, BE2, BE3	Brussels-Capital; Flemish; Walloon	Western Europe
Bulgaria (BG)	NUTS 3	BG311–BG425	28 regions including Sofia, Plovdiv, Varna, Burgas	Eastern Europe
Czechia (CZ)	NUTS 2	CZ01–CZ08	Praha, Jihozápad, Jihovýchod, Severozápad, etc.	Central Europe
Denmark (DK)	NUTS 2	DK01–DK05	Hovedstaden, Sjælland, Syddanmark, Midtjylland, Nordjylland	Northern Europe
Germany (DE)	NUTS 1	DE1–DEG	16 federal states (Länder)	Central Europe
Estonia (EE)	NUTS 3	EE001–EE008	Põhja-Eesti, Lääne-Eesti, Lõuna-Eesti, etc.	Northern Europe
Ireland (IE)	NUTS 3	IE041–IE063	Border, West, Mid-East, Dublin, etc.	Northern Europe
Greece (EL)	NUTS 2	EL30–EL65	Attiki, Peloponnisos, Kentriki Makedonia, etc.	Southern Europe
Spain (ES)	NUTS 2	ES11–ES70	17 autonomous communities	Southern Europe
France (FR)	NUTS 2	FRB0–FRM0	22 metropolitan regions	Western Europe
Croatia (HR)	NUTS 3	HR021–HR065	21 counties (županije)	Southern Europe
Italy (IT)	NUTS 2	ITC1–ITH5, ITI1–ITI4	20 regions	Southern Europe
Cyprus (CY)	NUTS 1	CY0	Whole country	Southern Europe
Latvia (LV)	NUTS 3	LV003–LV009	Kurzeme, Latgale, Riga, Pieriga, etc.	Northern Europe
Lithuania (LT)	NUTS 3	LT011–LT029	Vilnius, Kaunas, Klaipėda, etc.	Northern Europe
Luxembourg (LU)	NUTS 1	LU0	Whole country	Western Europe
Hungary (HU)	NUTS 3	HU110–HU333	20 counties (megye) + Budapest	Central Europe
Malta (MT)	NUTS 1	MT0	Whole country	Southern Europe
Netherlands (NL)	NUTS 2	NL11–NL42	12 provinces	Western Europe
Austria (AT)	NUTS 2	AT11–AT34	9 federal states	Central Europe
Poland (PL)	NUTS 2	PL21–PL84	16 voivodeships	Central Europe
Portugal (PT)	NUTS 2	PT11–PT30	Mainland and island regions	Southern Europe
Romania (RO)	NUTS 3	RO111–RO426	42 counties	Eastern Europe
Slovenia (SI)	NUTS 3	SI031–SI044	12 statistical regions	Southern Europe
Slovakia (SK)	NUTS 3	SK010–SK042	8 regions (kraje)	Central Europe
Finland (FI)	NUTS 2	FI1B–FI20	Helsinki-Uusimaa, Åland, etc.	Northern Europe
Sweden (SE)	NUTS 3	SE110–SE332	21 counties (län)	Northern Europe

Appendix B. Baseline medical cost for each country

Table B1. Medical cost per country (US\$).

Country	Medical costs			
	<i>Nuts 1 level</i>	<i>Emergency visit</i>	<i>Outpatient visit</i>	<i>Hospitalisation</i>
Austria		86.31	67.13	5065.86
Belgium		83.23	64.73	4771.47
Bulgaria		20.30	15.79	843.78
Croatia		28.65	22.28	1341.44
Cyprus		48.74	37.91	2630.85
Czech Republic		40.85	31.77	2082.24
Denmark		108.67	84.51	6317.06
Estonia		45.77	35.60	2206.83
Finland		86.93	67.61	5014.06
France		72.27	56.21	4055.93
Germany		85.22	66.28	4891.02
Greece		32.47	25.25	1736.50
Hungary		31.98	24.87	1522.36
Ireland		153.95	119.73	9312.65
Italy		56.90	44.26	3133.71
Latvia		33.61	26.14	1533.84
Lithuania		39.10	30.41	1834.99
Luxembourg		190.44	148.11	14 543.82
Malta		44.05	34.26	2918.28
Netherlands		87.77	68.26	5290.42
Poland		32.20	25.04	1463.68
Portugal		41.77	32.49	2115.83
Romania		24.97	19.42	1077.27
Slovakia		36.20	28.15	1781.46
Slovenia		48.23	37.51	2562.21
Spain		50.39	39.19	2780.71
Sweden		91.88	71.46	5378.75
EU		1702.84	1324.34	98 207.02

Appendix C. Heat-related Morbidity cases estimations.

Table C1. Hospitalisation preceded by emergency visits, long-term increase in baseline values under low and high emission climate scenarios.

Country	Times baseline			
	Low emission scenario		High emission scenario	
	2030	2070	2030	2070
Austria	2.1	3.4	2.2	7.2
Belgium	1.7	2.7	1.7	4.9
Bulgaria	2.0	2.5	2.1	5.5
Croatia	2.1	2.5	2.2	5.5
Cyprus	2.9	6.7	3.3	16.2
Czechia	1.9	3.0	2.1	5.8
Denmark	1.9	2.8	2.1	5.2
Estonia	1.8	2.5	1.9	4.3
Finland	1.8	2.3	1.9	4.1
France	2.1	3.4	2.2	7.2
Germany	1.7	2.2	1.8	4.0
Greece	2.7	4.1	2.8	9.7
Hungary	1.9	2.8	2.1	5.7
Ireland	2.5	6.2	2.7	13.3
Italy	2.2	2.9	2.3	7.1
Latvia	1.5	1.6	1.6	2.8
Lithuania	1.5	1.8	1.7	3.1
Luxembourg	2.0	5.4	2.2	10.6
Malta	4.6	11.6	5.1	32.9
Netherlands	2.0	3.0	2.1	5.1
Poland	2.0	3.4	2.3	6.3
Portugal	1.1	1.7	1.2	3.6
Romania	1.9	2.9	2.3	6.1
Slovakia	2.3	4.0	2.6	8.4
Slovenia	2.5	4.1	2.8	9.3
Spain	2.4	4.9	2.7	11.1
Sweden	1.6	2.6	1.7	4.4
Europe	1.9	2.9	2.1	6.0

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